

Appendix 4

Results

Figure 1: The results were classified into three categories according to the type of paper.

1. Model validation which measures how well the model works
2. Model effectiveness: This tests the model amongst a population and measures its effectiveness.
3. Preliminary study: suggesting a new design and how it impacts the test.

VALIDATION STUDIES

Figure 2: Representing the types of metrics used to evaluate the validation studies.

- MAD, AUC and F1 were only used once.
- MAD =median absolute deviation
- AUC = area under the s-curve
- Accuracy was the most used metric for the validation, followed by sensitivity and specificity.

Accuracy

Table 1: Representing accuracy between models in the validation studies.

Overall deep learning algorithms have better accuracy than machine learning.

Model used	Accuracy	Reference
DL object detection algorithm	93%	9
ML decision tree	94%	10
ML -	87%	13
ML -	85%	15
ML SVM	92%	16
ML SVM	97%	18
DL grad CAM	91%	19
DL IGWOCNN	100%	22

Sensitivity and specificity

Table 2: Sensitivity of each model

Model	Sensitivity	Reference
ML decision tree	94.7%	10
ML	87.3 %	15
ML SVM	100%	16
DL grad cam	98 %	19

Table 3: Specificity of each model

Model	Specificity	Reference
ML decision tree	94.4 %	10
ML	21.7 %	15
ML SVM	82 %	16
DL grad cam	95%	19

Discussion: ML used SVM had the highest sensitivity among the models. Followed by a deep learning model. While for specificity deep learning model performed better than all machine learning models.

Deep learning models are generally better than machine learning models when used in the medical education field.

MEDICAL EDUCATION:

Areas where machine learning was used in medical education. Classified mainly into simulation training, skill assessment, improved learning, and overall curriculum.

Figure 3: Demonstrating the different fields of medical education that AI was used in .

Discussion: AI was mostly used in simulation training. These include surgical skills like laparoscopic procedures or surgical suturing training. Skill assessment through interpreting actions and evaluating levels might give feedback. Improve teaching through better identification models and better and more available training. Evaluation of the curriculum by identifying missing areas in it.

Table 4: AI fields of interest in medical education

Field of interest	Number of studies	References
Simulation training	9	2,3,4,6,16,18,19,23,12
Skill assessment	6	8,9,1,4,15,17,22
Improve teaching	6	7,9,11,13,19,21,
Education curriculum evaluation	3	5,10,22

TYPE OF AI USED IN MEDICAL EDUCATION

Figure 4: Demonstrating types of AI used in medical education.

AI used	Number of studies	References
Machine learning	9	7,8,9,13,15,16,17,18,20
Deep learning	6	4,9,11,19,21,22
Virtual reality	7	2,3,5,6,15,17,23
Natural language processing	4	13,14,19,11

Table 5: Types of AI used in medical education.

The most used type of AI was machine learning algorithms, followed by virtual reality and then deep learning and natural language processing.

Natural Language Processing studies:

Table 6: Different uses of natural language processing in medical education

NLP uses	No of studies	Reference
Improve presentation quality	1	13
Students' assessment through feedback	3	14,19,11

Figure 5: Demonstrate different uses of natural language processing in medical education.

Discussion: Natural language processing was used to evaluate and assess students' educational levels through processing feedback from teaching, previous evaluations, and comments on their work .it also improves presentation quality by identifying where the presentations might lack in this field

Visual reality studies:

Table 7: Different uses of virtual reality in medical education

VR uses	No of studies	References
Surgical skills training	5	2,3,6,17,23
Skills assessment	1	15
Enhance learning effectiveness	1	5

Figure 6: Demonstrate different uses of virtual reality in medical education.

Discussion: Virtual reality applications are mostly related to surgical training skills through simulation training, showing the right way to do the procedure. It can be repeated several times and enhance teaching by adding mal teaching methods.

Machine learning:

Table 8: Demonstrate different areas of Machine Learning algorithms in medical education.

ML uses	Number of studies	Reference
Learning through identification	2	7,13
Skill enhancement	2	17,20
Performance assessment	3	8,16,18
Curriculum assessment	2	10,15

Figure 7: Demonstrate different areas of Machine Learning algorithms in medical education.

Discussion: Machine learning is the most used type of AI in this study. It helps students identify diseases through histopathological features and improve their skills by taking them step by step for better understanding. It helps enhance curriculums and assessment of students' performance in a specific task or overall assessment.

Deep learning studies:

Table 9: showing the applications of deep learning in medical education.

DL applications	Number of studies	Reference
Teaching	4	4,11,19,21
Assessment	1	9
Curriculum assessment	1	22

Table 8: Applications of deep learning in medical education.

Chart 4: showing the applications of deep learning in medical education.

Discussion: Deep learning is used in teaching by deconstructing video or images or any data and highlighting specific targets that will aid in better understanding and better performance. It is also used with NLP to analyze large data in curriculums and identify their shortcomings.

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